

Project website and Public Relations

Action Acronym: PEACE

Action title: Project 101101343 - Pressurized Efficient Alkaline Electrolyser

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PEACE Consortium

Beneficiary name	Short name
Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V. (DE)	DLR
Materials Mates Italia SRL (IT)	MMI
Technische Universiteit Eindhoven (NL)	TU/e
Brandenburgische Technische Universität Cottbus Senftenberg (DE)	BTU CS
Grant Garant sro (CZ)	GG
HyCC B.V. (NL)	HYCC
Danmarks Tekniske Universitet (DK)	DTU

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AEL	Alkaline Electrolysis
CHP	Clean Hydrogen Partnership
EU	European Union
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
M	Month
PEDR	Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results
PR	Public Relations

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1. Executive Summary

This document summarises the tools that will be used to promote the PEACE project and its results. The PEACE project is a research and innovation action funded by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership (CHP) under the Horizon Europe programme. The PEACE project is coordinated by Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V. (DLR). The main objective of the project is to reduce the levelized cost of hydrogen via development of an innovative high-pressure alkaline electrolysis technology for hydrogen production.

This report is based on a PEACE deliverable of the same name which was delivered to the granting authority in month (M) 6 of the project implementation – i.e., November 2023. The present report is produced for public use and its main aim is to present the wide variety of public relations (PR) tools that PEACE will have at hand to raise interest in its results within the target audience. The presented tools are part of PEACE complex Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR) (see more at: <https://www.h2peace.eu/public-media/results>). The management of the PEACE PR actions is ensured by the WP6 leader (GG). The Coordinator (DLR) approves all communication items before publishing.

The communication tools were selected to enable effective PR actions and to reach the PEACE target audience with key communication messages. One of the main PEACE PR tools is the project branding. PEACE visual identity consists of project logo and typography, including deliverables and presentations templates.

The cornerstone of project PR is the [PEACE website](#), providing rich information about the project, its results and news.

The online PR campaign of the project is supported by PEACE social media profiles on [X](#) and [LinkedIn](#).

Printed parts PR items consist of the PEACE project info-flyer and the PEACE roll up banner. They are assumed to be used during events participation.

Finally, PEACE newsletter and press releases will be used for project communication and dissemination purposes.

2. PEACE Project Summary

The PEACE project represents a challenging research and innovation action in the field of hydrogen production, using the alkaline electrolysis (AEL) technologies. AEL technologies are known for their low investment costs and excellent scalability. The PEACE project aims to further improve the levelized cost of hydrogen produced by AEL. Therefore, efforts are focused on enhancing efficiency, maximizing current densities, and enabling better integration with downstream processes. By carefully designing a high-pressure stack and system, the performance and overall efficiency of the AEL process will be significantly improved, eliminating the need for additional compression for downstream processes. This, in turn, reduces the capital and operational expenses associated with hydrogen compressors, which are a substantial part of electrolysis systems' cost.

Within the PEACE project, a demonstrator of an AEL system exceeding 50 kW, capable of operating at pressures more than 50 bar, will be designed and developed. This is achieved through a novel concept involving two-stage pressurization. The integration of advanced components, innovative design, and optimized operation strategies will be explored through modelling and experimental testing, ultimately aiming to demonstrate a system with impressive efficiency characteristics. The successful implementation of this technology promises a significant reduction in the cost of green hydrogen production.

The PEACE project scientific objectives are reinforced by a strong focus on sustainability and circularity aspects, as well as dedicated outreach activities. The consortium comprises two SMEs, four research and development centres with established expertise in alkaline stack, system, and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), and one of the largest hydrogen production and utilization companies globally. This collaboration ensures a comprehensive approach to achieving the project's goals.

Finally, the project aims to propose use cases and the concept of an integrated plant. By combining all these developments, the goal is to achieve a technological breakthrough with a clear commercial perspective, positioning Europe as a leader in highly pressurized AEL technology within the next three years.

3. Objectives of the deliverable

PEACE is a research and innovation action project funded by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership under the Horizon Europe programme. The PEACE project is coordinated by Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V. (DLR) and it started in June 2023. The main objective for the 36 months of implementation of the project is to reduce the levelized cost of hydrogen via development of an innovative high-pressure alkaline electrolysis technology for hydrogen production.

Simultaneously, the PEACE ultimate goal is to further disseminate the results to wider audience and turn PEACE research & innovation actions into concrete value and impact for society by exploiting the results. To achieve these goals, a complex Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR) has been produced as a deliverable (see more at: <https://www.h2peace.eu/public-media/results>). The PEDR explains in detail how the consortium will coherently promote the research and innovation action and its results towards multiple audiences.

The present report “Project Website and PR” is closely interlinked to the PEDR as it describes **the tools that will be used to promote the project and its results**. It summarises the initial activities of the WP6 “Circularity, dissemination, exploitation and communication” that have been done in the first 6 months of PEACE implementation to prepare the necessary tools which will be used mainly for communication purposes of the project.

By PR, it is meant “Public Relations”, a strategic communication process to build positive relationship with the public and other relevant target groups. Following the EC definitions, it needs to be stressed that by “communication” we mean to take measures in order to inform the target groups about the project and its activities, about project’s further use and benefits. “Dissemination” actions are defined as public disclosure of the results by appropriate means (e.g. publications, conference presentations). By “exploitation” we mean the use of results in further research/innovation activities or results’ commercial exploitation.

This document is a living platform of tools and promotional activities and will be updated during the project life cycle upon need.

4. PEACE PR management

This report has been prepared by the WP6 leader GRANT Garant (GG) which is the entity responsible for PEACE project PR and communication plan implementation. The objective of PEACE communication measures is to reach out to society and show the impact and benefits of PEACE by addressing and providing possible solutions to propelling global carbon neutrality by accelerating the European hydrogen industry. Communication measures will inform about and promote the project and its results to multiple audiences.

GG prepares tools for effective PR and addresses the PEACE target groups (see Chapter 5) with key messages (see more on this in [PEACE PEDR](#)). The PR management includes the Coordinator (DLR), as all communication items (including social media posts and website articles) are approved by the Coordinator beforehand. The consortium members contribute to the PR of the project in two ways – they provide GG the background scientific material for promotional items production, if needed, and actively participate in project communication, dissemination and exploitation activities as described within the PEDR.

5. PR tools

The PR tools that will be presented below were produced in order to address the PEACE target groups defined by the PEDR. Project communication will be tailored to approach:

- 1) **Research communities** (including university students, research audience and complementary innovation projects)
- 2) **European institutions** (including hydrogen-oriented networks)
- 3) **Industry and business**
- 4) **Public and media**

5.1. Branding

The project branding enables the consortium to promote PEACE actions and results in a uniform manner. PEACE visual identity consists of **project logo and typography** recommendations. They were produced under the guidance of GG by a creative digital agency. The final selection of the project logo (three options were available) was done by PEACE Executive Board members voting in M2 of project implementation. The PEACE logo (Fig. 1) is built on the notion of green hydrogen. It is accompanied by typography recommendations for particular font type, size and colour (so called logo-manual).

Fig 1. PEACE logo in colour and black-and-white version

For the purpose of project communication and dissemination, the logo file along with the PEACE logo-manual are stored at the PEACE internal team site and are available to all consortium members for download.

5.2. Templates

Consortium members can use a ready-made Microsoft **Word template** for PEACE reports/deliverables (see below in Fig. 2 the title page and page 2), following the visual identity of the project.

Fig. 2 PEACE deliverable template

Alongside, Microsoft **PowerPoint template** (see in Fig. 3 the opening and closing slide) have been created for the use of the PEACE consortium.

Fig. 3 PEACE PowerPoint presentation template

The templates can be downloaded at the PEACE internal team site and are available to all consortium members.

5.3. Website

The PEACE **project website** <https://www.h2peace.eu/> is the core of the PEACE communication plan. It enables the information flow especially towards the public and media target group, and industry and business audience. The main goal is to share the basic information about the project itself, its setting within the broader context of the Green Deal discussion, and about project findings and updates.

An enormous work effort has been targeted to website establishment, its design and content. The website preparation as well as maintenance is arranged for by the WP6 leader GG. The PEACE website, following the project visual identity creation, was established in M2 and after several rounds of internal controls, checks and all consortium approval went public in M6. It will be updated with up-to-date information on project development.

The PEACE **Homepage** includes basic facts about the project, project objectives, latest news as well as the structure of the consortium (see Fig. 4). Obligatory visual identity items of the funding institutions - EC and CHP belong to main website components. The top bar consists of project logo, links to website pages (About; News & Events; Consortium; Public & Media), and links to project X and LinkedIn profiles. A contact form is included. Moreover, the lower bar contains GDPR and Cookies section, with Imprint in the footer.

Fig. 5 Sitemap of the PEACE website

The PEACE website includes pages on project objectives and workplan (sub-page for each WPs) and presents all consortium members. A special page for Public & Media is delineated, introducing basic facts about the project in non-professional language and representing a marketplace for all project communication and dissemination outcomes (flyer, press releases, newsletter, publications, reports). Importantly, a sub-page is dedicated to project news, including events to be visited/hosted by PEACE team members.

The structure and content of the website had been approved by all consortium members before the website went public.

5.4. Info-flyer

To reach public & media, as well as industrial and business partners, a **project info-flyer** has been prepared under the guidance of GG. It is a trifold flyer with basic facts about the PEACE project in a ready-to-be-printed format. It can be downloaded directly from the [PEACE website](#). Internal storage of the document is guaranteed at the PEACE internal team site.

Fig. 6 PEACE info-flyer

MEET THE PEACE PROJECT

WHAT

is PEACE?

Research and innovation project within the Horizon Europe programme

Funded by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership

Started in June 2023

Developing an innovative technology of high-pressure alkaline electrolysis (AEL) to produce hydrogen

PEACE technology will be green, efficient, less expensive and with low adverse environmental impact

WHY

does PEACE take action?

To significantly decrease the hydrogen production cost and to boost the hydrogen economy

To contribute to reduction of emission of carbon dioxide

To increase the energy efficiency of hydrogen production

WHICH

objectives has PEACE set itself?

Development of highly efficient pressurized stack

Pressure vessel stack concept

Balance of Plant and auxiliary optimization and qualifications

Technology demonstration

Integration concept with downstream chemical plants

Reduction of capital costs per system

HOW

does PEACE work?

- 1** Qualification of various cell and stack components
- 2** Assembling of the PEACE AEL stack demonstrator with the best-performing components
- 3** Demonstrator enrichment with dual-stage pressurisation concept
- 4** Demonstrator in operation - evaluation of function, performance and characteristics simulations
- 5** Assessment of the environmental and other impacts of the PEACE technology, and PEACE AEL integration with a chemical plant directly utilising the PEACE-produced hydrogen

WHO

is PEACE?

The PEACE consortium is composed of 7 entities from 5 EU countries under the coordination of Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt (DLR).

5.5. Roll up banner

A project roll up banner (Fig. 7) has been produced by GG. The banner should boost project promotion at events and exhibitions. The banner is prepared in a ready-to-be-printed format and is destined for download by consortium members at the PEACE internal team site.

Fig. 7 PEACE roll up banner

5.6. Social media profiles

Social media are highly valuable communication channel for the PEACE project, targeting at all PEACE audience groups. Regular posting by the WP6 leader (after Coordinator’s approval) is envisaged. PEACE consortium agreed to use two project social media profiles – one on X, and one on LinkedIn. Both are using the hashtag: **#peaceh2**. Profiles are built on PEACE visual identity.

GG has established, maintains and feeds the PEACE project profile on **X** (https://twitter.com/peace_h2; username: @peace_h2). X posts will be mainly used to deliver the key messages to the public and media.

Fig. 8 PEACE X account

Simultaneously, GG runs and feeds the PEACE project profile on **LinkedIn** (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/h2peace/>; @PEACE H2 project). Posts are targeted more towards scientific and industrial community.

Fig. 9 PEACE LinkedIn account

5.7. Newsletter

Promotion of the PEACE project will be boosted by PEACE **newsletter** (12 issues are planned). PEACE newsletter issues are planned to reach readers by email (subscription form available on the project website: <https://www.h2peace.eu/newsletter>), through PEACE social media profiles and will be downloadable at the website. Consortium members are expected to distribute the newsletter within their institutional and professional networks.

The project newsletter is built on PEACE visual identity (see Issue#1 in Fig. 10). The newsletter is produced by GG – inputs from consortium members will be asked for. The content of each issue is approved by the Coordinator. PEACE newsletter will mainly present information about the project and its results, including an editorial of the Coordinator. Special sections are dedicated to news in the world of hydrogen and to upcoming events. Final section of the newsletter presents open calls for funding of hydrogen project proposals.

Fig. 10 PEACE Newsletter

5.8. Press releases

PEACE project will use press releases for its communication and dissemination purposes. Six press releases are assumed to be circulated. Their content will be prepared by the WP6 leader upon inputs from scientific members of the consortium.

6. Conclusion

The present PEACE report has been produced by the WP6 leader (GG) in April 2024 as a public output of the project. Its main aim is to present the tools that PEACE will use to promote itself and its results towards multiple audience. The tools were selected to enable effective PR actions and to reach the PEACE target audience with key communication messages.

One of the main PR tools is the project branding. PEACE visual identity consists of project logo and typography, including deliverables and presentations templates. The PEACE logo is built around the notion of green hydrogen and is consistently used in all external communication materials.

The cornerstone of project PR is the [PEACE website](#). A structured website, based on PEACE visual identity, provides rich information about the project itself, its setting within the broader context of the Green Deal discussion, and about project results and news. It provides a living communication and dissemination platform.

The online PR campaign of the project is supported by PEACE social media profiles on [X](#) and [LinkedIn](#).

Printed parts of the PR campaign consist of the PEACE project info-flyer and the PEACE roll up banner. They are assumed to be used during events participation.

Finally, PEACE newsletter and press releases will be used to communicate the project towards its audience.